

Median Arcuate Ligament Syndrome in an Elderly Patient: Diagnostic Challenges and Laparoscopic Management

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Introduction

Median arcuate ligament syndrome (MALS), also known as Dunbar syndrome, is a rare vascular condition caused by compression of the celiac artery by the median arcuate ligament. It is characterized by postprandial abdominal pain, nausea, bloating, vomiting, and weight loss.

Case Presentation

A 71-year-old woman presented to the Regional Institute of Gastroenterology and Hepatology with abdominal pain, postprandial bloating, and significant weight loss (8 kg over the past two months). The diagnostic challenge in this case was due to multiple comorbidities, including antral gastritis, chronic idiopathic constipation, and irritable bowel syndrome, as well as the increased risk of malignancy at this age. Consequently, the diagnosis was established by exclusion. Paraclinical evaluation included Doppler ultrasound, computed tomography angiography, and conventional angiography, all of which confirmed compression of the celiac artery. The therapeutic goal was to restore normal blood flow by decompression of the celiac artery. The surgical procedure consisted of division of the median arcuate ligament and celiac ganglionectomy to interrupt sympathetic nerve fibers, thereby reducing neurogenic pain and preventing persistent postoperative symptoms. Revascularization of the celiac artery was also performed. A laparoscopic approach was preferred due to its advantages, including reduced postoperative pain, shorter hospital stay, lower complication rates, and faster recovery. The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on postoperative day four. Follow-up Doppler ultrasound at one month demonstrated normal celiac artery blood flow, with complete resolution of symptoms.

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of considering MALS in elderly patients presenting with nonspecific abdominal symptoms, especially in the presence of multiple comorbidities.

Keywords

celiac artery, laparoscopic decompression, Dunbar syndrome